

NanoOrgano – drapable preforms from nano-modified hybrid yarns for the production of thermoplastic composites

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The paper presents a current research project “NanoOrgano” funded by the Federal German Ministry of Education and Research. The research started in November 2008. Within the project, a new technology for production of drapable nano-modified thermoplastic preforms is being developed. This allows simultaneous impregnation and consolidation of composites with higher impact strength and energy absorption.

Keywords: textile reinforced thermoplastics, thermoplastic composites, nano-modification, filament yarns, melt spinning, hybrid yarns, commingling, impact strength

Preliminaries

Textile reinforced thermoplastics are composite materials, which continually gains on importance. For their production, mainly pre-consolidated thermoplastic preforms, in form of stiff plates, are used. In a following step, these thermoplastic “prepregs” are being heated and additionally formed to structural parts by moulding. However, the production process in two steps is time- and cost-consuming [1]. Therefore, there is a need for a new technology, which allows the efficient production of thermoplastic composites with enhanced mechanical properties in a single process step.

The application of hybrid yarns offers such a technology. These hybrid structures contain the reinforcement and thermoplastic matrix in form of continuous filaments. The hybrid yarns are further processed to textiles, which can be consolidated and formed to a structural part in a single moulding step. Such hybrid yarns are already commercially available, however only in combination of glass and polypropylene [2]. In order to enlarge the fields of application for these thermoplastic prepregs, new material combinations are needed.

Goal of the project

In collaboration of research institutes and industrial companies, a new technology for the cost-efficient production of composite parts with improved mechanical properties is being developed.

Solution concept

The new technology bases on the development and application of nano-modified semi-consolidated thermoplastic preforms for the production of composite structures. Due to the nano-modification of the thermoplastic matrix different mechanical properties of the composite, like impact and energy absorption, should be improved [3],[4]. The material- and process-chain of the project are given by Figure 1.

Figure 1: Material- and process-chain

Using the melt-spinning technology, the thermoplastic nano-compound is further processed to continuous filament yarns. In a following process step the new nano-modified polyamide (PA) filaments and different types of Aramid yarns are commingled to hybrid yarn structures. These are further processed to multi-axial non-crimp fabrics with a surface weight of app. 400 g/m². The multi-axial structures represent semi-consolidated thermoplastic pre-form with textile character. They can be easily draped into the desired form and, after heating beyond the melting point of the thermoplastic component, moulded to composite structural parts.

Experimental works

The experimental works described in this paper are being presented according the technological order given by Figure 1.

Compounding of nano-particles in PA

Within the research project, different types of TiO₂ and BaSO₄ nano-particles, developed by the Company Sachtleben Chemie GmbH, Duisburg, Germany are being investigated. Table 1 gives an overview of the particle types used within the research project.

Table 1: Nano-particles investigated within the project “NanoOrgano”

Particle type	Material	Particle size [nm]
RM300	TiO ₂	15
R210	TiO ₂	300
N20	BaSO ₄	20
HP	BaSO ₄	200

The compounding of nano-particles into the polymer was carried out at the Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe (IVW) of the Technical University Kaiserslautern, Germany. Beside the prevention of the polymer degradation, the homogeneous and agglomerate free distribution of nano-particles into the polymer is the most important requirement to the compounding process. Figure 2 shows typical particle distribution in PA compound.

Figure 2: Particle distribution in compound, cleavage fracture [Source: IVW]

In order to investigate the influence of the nano-particle, their size and amount of the melt-spinning behaviour of the compound as well as of the mechanical properties of the composite, compounds with different particles and concentrations (low – 1 % and high - 8 %) were produced at IVW. Table 2 gives an overview of the produced compounds.

Table 2: Compound for the preliminary tests

Compound	Particle type	Particle content Vol.-%
PA	-	-
PA + 1 Vol. % RM300	TiO ₂	1
PA + 8 Vol. % RM300	TiO ₂	8
PA + 1 Vol. % R210	TiO ₂	1
PA + 1 Vol. % N20	BaSO ₄	1
PA + 8 Vol. % N20	BaSO ₄	8
PA + 1 Vol. % HP	BaSO ₄	1

Continuous filament yarns in labor scale

With the previously described compounds preliminary melt-spinning-tests in labor scale were carried out at Institut für Textiltechnik (ITA) of the RWTH Aachen University, Germany. The preliminary tests were accomplished at a piston spinning plant of the company Fourné Polymertechnik GmbH, Alter, Germany (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Melt-spinning of nano-modified PA

Due to the construction of the piston spinning plant, there are no further possibilities to dissolve the agglomerates. Quite the contrary during the melting of the compound, new and bigger agglomerates are formed up. This has a negative influence of the process stability and of the distribution quality of the particles in the yarn. A visual evidence for the forming of new agglomerates gives the Figure 4.

Figure 4: Agglomerates in the cross-section of the filaments

However offers the piston spinning plant a time- and cost-efficient possibility to investigate the melt spinning behaviour of the compounds. The accomplished tests have shown that, particle concentrations into the filaments up to 8 Vol.-% (approx. 54 Weight-%) can be achieved. However, the process stability decreases with a higher particle degree, so a balance between these two factors should be found.

Up-scaling the melt-spinning technology

The up-scaling of the melt-spinning process for the production of nano-modified PA continuous filaments was recently carried out at ITA. The experimental series were accomplished at the Melt spinning machine A100 made by the company BASF AG, Ludwigshafen, Germany shown in

Figure 5: Melt spinning machine A100

Due to the systematic investigation of the spin-packages and the accomplishment of extensive parameter studies, nano-modified PA filament yarns with up to 4 Vol.-% (approx. 15 Weight-%) nano-particles were produced.

The up-scaling tests have clearly shown that, the higher concentration of nano-particles in compound leads to clogging of the spin-packages. Wider filter meshes increase the endurance of the spin-packages, however the stability and the efficiency of the process decrease dramatically.

Investigation of the mechanical properties

In order to investigate the influence of the nano-particles on the mechanical properties of the polymer and to characterize the polymer degradation as a result of the compounding and extrusion process, the tensile strength of the filament yarns were determined according DIN EN ISO 2062.

Since the yarns produced at the A100 melt-spinning plant are being currently investigated, there are no consolidated findings about their mechanical properties.

The mechanical properties presented in this paper belong to the different filament yarns produced on the piston spinning plant within the described preliminary tests.

As it can be seen in Figure 6, the average level of the tensile strength for all of the yarns produced within the preliminary test (approx. 10 -15 cN/tex) is very low – POY usually 40 to 50 cN/tex. This can be explained with the low orientation and crystallisation of the macro-molecules as a result of the process-related lower spinn- and filament-drawing.

However the results of the tests have shown that despite of the polymer degradation due to the additional compounding process, the tensile strength of the nano-modified filament yarns match approximately the tensile strength of the pure polymer. So, it can be guaranteed that basic yarn strength, sufficient for the further processing is given.

Figure 6: Comparison of the tensile strength of the yarns

In order to analyse the influence of the nano-particles on the impact strength and the energy absorption extensive mechanical tests on the basic compound as well as on filament yarns produced at the melt-spinning plant A100 are being currently carried out at the IVW. Thus, the modification degree respectively the particle concentration with the best material performance should be determined.

Prospect

Even though the first up-scaling tests accomplished at ITA were very promising, some further extended research is necessary to increase the efficiency and stability of the melt-spinning process.

In the next step, according the material- and process-chain in Figure 1, commingling yarns made of the nano-modified PA yarns and Aramid should be developed. The manufacturing of the hybrid yarns is scheduled for the end of 2009. First textile structures, woven and bi-axial non-crimp fabrics should be produced during the first half of 2010. The development of the consolidation process and the moulding of the structural parts is intended in the course of 2010.

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